

D5.2 Interim report on linking channels of dissemination and Altmetrics – methodology report

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Abbreviations

ALM- Article Level Metrics

EC – European Commission

PloS – Public Library of science

PMB – Project Management Board

Q – Question Battery

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Table 1: Dissemination Channels

Table 2: Data Provider

Summary

This report aims to provide a methodology to construct and present a taxonomy that links innovative channels of dissemination with alternative or open metrics. The taxonomy we will construct provides orientation for scholars who intend to make use of these channels. The taxonomy is also useful for scholars who want/need? to assess or reflect about their usage. Based on the considerations of the sociology of valuation, we came up with different dimensions that constitute relevant dimensions, e.g., discourses, cultural (field specific) practices, and metrics. We provide the following approach to translate and enrich these theoretical concepts with empirical analysis conducted within OpenUp.

Firstly, to reconstruct dominant narratives and discourses, we build a review of scholarly literature about Altmetrics and innovative dissemination channels, relating to Deliverables 4.1. and 5.1., respectively.

Secondly, to map perceptions and public of these channels and Altmetrics indicators, we draw on the survey conducted within OpenUp that has been designed by all project participants coordinated and implemented by the PM. These data allow specifying general structures and field specific information.

Thirdly, these data have been validated by explorative interviews with experts in the field to reconstruct dominant interpretive patterns.

Finally, this information will be synthesized and discussed with interested communities to further deepen the resulting taxonomy. We provided preliminary results that allowed for some specification of these dimensions.

After all the empirical analysis and interpretation, we will provide a taxonomy where each channel of dissemination is linked to specific information about its appreciation, field specificity, and relation to scholarly or societal discourse. An overview of possible outcome is provided in chapter 4.

We hope that the derived taxonomy might also stimulate debate about the uses and problems with innovative channels of dissemination and their current counting practices.

1. Introduction

This report provides orientation for scholars who intend to make use of innovative types of dissemination channels or are about to critically assess or reflect about their usage. In a previous report, we have put forward the idea that different channels of scholarly dissemination are attributed value in various practices of usage, appreciation, and measurement (Deliverable 5.1.).¹ Based on what we have called ‘acts of valuation’, these different channels have a certain medium inherent value. That is, worth which is derived by the specific function it seeks to provide, beside dissemination, such as entertaining, organizing attribution and so on. In addition, these medium based value attributions of channels of dissemination are valorised through classifications, indicators, scholarly debates, and cultures of appreciation in their disciplines.

Our goal is to develop a taxonomy of different channels of dissemination which are linked to various dimensions of appreciation and evaluation. The taxonomy which we intend to provide is on the one hand derived from theoretical considerations based on the sociology of valuation, but also empirically grounded. We provide dimensions of appreciation based on scholarly debates. We also present context specific characteristics of these dimensions by relating them to factors such as age or field specificity. Scholars are provided resources to critically assess whether the dissemination channels are suitable for and appreciated by the audience they intend to reach. Since new metrics of research communication output increasingly influence scholarly practices we will also provide how each channel of dissemination is measured by different providers and data services. Our hope is that the taxonomy will not only inform scholarly strategies but also stimulate debates.

The report is structured as follows: In the following section (chapter 2), we will review the literature about taxonomies and present the strategic approach for constructing dimensions in this report. Subsequently (chapter 3), the methodological approach, material, and data that inform or a going to inform the taxonomy will be presented. In chapter 4, we will present the different dimensions of the channels of dissemination and their significance for scholarly strategies. In the concluding section (chapter 5), we will provide an outlook of how the results of the various empirical activities will inform the taxonomy and stimulate wider debates.

2. Theoretical framework for constructing taxonomy of dissemination channels

What are taxonomies? Taxonomies are attempts to classify entities according to their properties and to certain dimensions (Bailey 1994). They have excluding and including effects on the entities of the social or physical world they claim to represent (Bowker, Star 1999). In academic settings, taxonomies are used to conceptualise complex phenomena with interrelated issues that are often not immediately conveyable (Smith 2002). By arranging and ordering different entities into specific categories, they reduce complexity and can provide a framework for debate (Greenberg 1987; Archibugi 2006), but also for intervention (Bradley et al. 2007). In this support activity, our task is to develop a taxonomy that provides orientation to scholars preparing or evaluating a dissemination strategy for their research output. Since dissemination of research is a complex phenomenon, many different aspects come to the fore of which not all can be related to the content but to cultural characteristics, such as routines, norms, and values of their target audiences.

¹ http://openup-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/OpenUp-Deliverable_D5.1_Altmetrics-status-quo.pdf

How are taxonomies constructed, given these complexities? As other types of frameworks such as theories, themes, or typologies, they are constructed through a complex interplay between reflection and observation. Yet different to typologies which are perceived to represent abstract concepts, taxonomies are understood to relate to ‘empirically observable and measurable characteristics (Smith 2002, p. 381). Hence, taxonomies are based on empirical observation and validation that relates to these characteristics. This often entails engaging experts or conducting surveys to explore perceptions or patterns of interpretation.

The empirical analysis and exploration that allows the specification of taxonomies, however, hinges on theoretical considerations that constitute and can inform how a phenomenon is articulated and how dimensions are constructed that relate to each other.² In this project, we intend to construct a taxonomy of dissemination channels based on considerations from the sociology of valuation that provides key assumptions about how different scholarly services become relevant and valuable for scholarly dissemination and for what reasons. As outlined in a previous report, the basis for such theory making is that evaluation becomes more important (Power 1997) because of the increasing uncertainty and complexity in many different fields of society. This particularly accounts for scholarly communication and dissemination, which has been traditionally safeguarded by the institutions of peer review and other mechanisms of self-governance. These mechanisms of self-governance have provided scholarly dissemination channels such as articles, books and with value and appreciation both within and beyond the scholarly realm (Merton 1957, 1968). Moreover, a specific set of evaluation indicators and metrics has been constructed on these channels of dissemination and the way they refer to each other (e.g. in publications and citations). From the perspective of the sociology of valuation (Lamont 2012), these metrics have provided additional value to these channels since they represent abstract concepts such as performance or disciplinary recognition. With the advent of new channels of dissemination and the appreciation they are about to gain in different realms of society and their audiences, it becomes unclear how these are to be perceived and valorised. This task of OpenUp (5.2. and 5.4) seeks to contribute to a clarification in this respect. What we can interestingly observe is thus: value creation in the making.

In the previous report, we have argued that the way these channels are attributed value is through both their use and consumption. Specific qualities of these channels are infused with values which are regarded relevant for specific purposes. The qualities that these channels have for their users and their audiences, we have argued, cause their significance for scholarly communication since they are not necessarily explicitly known but literally enacted every single time a specific item is produced or consumed. Based on extensive literature review, we have called these action ‘acts as valuation’ whereby we classified various activities in digital scholarly services and social media to the following concepts: doing science and science made public (e.g. blogs, microblogs), referencing (Mendeley), entertainment (e.g. youtube, vimeo), stabilizing knowledge (Wikipedia, github etc.), recommending (e.g. f1000), and organizing attribution. In our theoretical framework, these acts of valuation constitute the phenomena to which different dimensions can be attached which will be outlined in the following sections.

The dimensions of these channels are constructed through various processes we intend to explore. On the one hand, they are constructed through discourses that attribute value to a certain channel of communication by positioning them to a dominant narrative. In the realm of scholarly communication, such a dominant discourse is the discourse about research performance or research impact that can influence how a certain channel of dissemination can be valorised. For instance, the quantitatively

² For example, in the case of policy studies, the most important taxonomy is constructed from the basic assumption that politics is caused by policies, hence, that political structures are the effects of the processual dimensions.

informed research performance discourse has altered how book chapters are perceived. In a similar way, we argue, new discourses have developed that shapes how a certain novel channel is perceived.

The second process, which influences how certain channels of dissemination are perceived, are existing cultural practices and routines. Becher and Trowler have put forward the idea that the different disciplines in science can be understood as specific tribes that govern a particular territory of science, challenging the notion that science is understood as an abstract unity (Becher, Trowler 1989). Specific practices and stances which have been incorporated through scientific socialization processes shape how a specific format of communicating science is performed. For instance, Charles Bazerman has shown how the structure and writing format of scientific research article enact how physical science is to be understood (Bazerman 1988). At the contrary in sociology, the production of large monographs value has long been highly recognized, as disciplinary histories reconstructed the field by referring to sociological founding fathers that made use of these formats (Weingart, Lepenies 1983). Through these culturally and field-specific writing and consumption habits, specific channels are attributed value. New channels of dissemination, we propose, will be to some extent estimated against how appropriate they are in accordance with existing field specific valuations of certain channels of dissemination. In this respect, we might also expect generational differences that cut across these various domains of science.

Thirdly and finally, we argue that the value of these channels of dissemination will be influenced by how they are integrated into certain metrics. Quantitative indicators in science strongly refer to categories of evaluation. Metrics are rarely neutral objects. Consequently, the significance of some communication channels might hinge on how they are tracked and counted. In addition, these counting and tracking activities of novel channels of dissemination are performed by specific providers who integrate several of these channels as data sources in their metric (e.g. PloS ALM, altmetric.com, Plum Analytics). These providers display differences as to how they relate and integrate these data sources. For scholarly strategies, that means that scholars might not only look at what channels they use, e.g. which kind of value they want to create by choosing a specific format, but also whether this kind of activity is covered by altmetrics providers that are most appropriate for their community.

Based on the above theoretical framework, we provide our approach to cover the different channels of dissemination, their dimensions, and their valuation.

3. Approach, data, and methodology

3.1. General approach:

Based on these theoretical considerations, our aim is to study discourses, field specific perceptions, and metrics of innovative channels of dissemination. These empirical data will be used to inform and to specify the different dimensions related to the specific acts of valuation we proposed.

To study discourses around innovative dissemination and altmetrics, an analysis of scholarly publications and positions appears to be most suitable since these discourses are most likely to shape legitimate positions and thereby construct value to their use and consumption.

To directly study how innovative channels of dissemination are recognized, and to learn more about the structural aspects thereof, the most common technique is to develop and conduct a survey that can provide information about common perceptions. While this information can most likely reveal what is known and perceived relevant, more qualitative interviews reveal how the significance of certain dissemination channels is interpreted and what drives this interpretation that leads to value creation in scholarly and non-scholarly debates.

Finally, in order to create what Nowotny et al. call robust knowledge (Nowotny et al. 2001), the resulting knowledge taxonomy needs to be related to the relevant audiences and stakeholders in order to stimulate debate and allow for participation in creating reflexive resources (see also Deliverable 4.1. in this respect). All these different perspectives of inquiry demand different and tailored methods of data collection that need to be designed in accordance with the guiding research question of this activity, which is, constructing a theoretically informed and empirically grounded taxonomy of dissemination channels.

Within OpenUp, we can draw on various activities of data collection and exploration that meet these demands which altogether aim at contributing to a triangulation and validation of the subject under study.

Firstly, to reconstruct dominant narratives and discourses, we can build on a review of scholarly literature about Altmetrics and innovative dissemination channels, relating to Deliverables 4.1. and 5.1., respectively.

Secondly, to map perceptions and public of these channels and altmetric indicators, we can draw on a survey conducted within OpenUp that has been designed by all project participants coordinated and implemented by the coordinator. These data allow specifying general structures and field-specific information. These data will also allow for integrating gender related aspects.

Thirdly, these data will be validated by explorative interviews with experts in the field in order to reconstruct dominant interpretive patterns.

Finally, all this information will be synthesized and discussed with interested communities to further deepen the resulting taxonomy. In the following, we provide data and method of each activity in detail.

3.2. Data, methods, and preliminary results

3.2.1. Analysis of scholarly discourse

Firstly, we can build on previous work in Deliverable 5.1. In that report, we have analysed a corpus of around 320 articles and position papers to reconstruct the landscape of how innovative dissemination channels are framed (see Appendix A for details). By applying bibliometric and informetric methods in attempts of constructing the corpus (see Moed et al. 2004 for an overview), we revealed which communities were active and thus particularly shaped their meaning, which is, informetric and scientometric community. We observed a sharp increase of publications on these topics allowing for predicting with some uncertainty that the debate towards dissemination is continuing to thrive. After having grouped and classified these various pieces of communication, we have identified two major discourses to which innovative dissemination is related. Probably, it is these channels that do not only frame how innovative dissemination and altmetrics are understood but that also influence their recent uptake.

The first discourse to which Altmetrics is related to is the discourse on research performance and impact of research (Bornmann, Leydesdorff 2013; Costas et al. 2014; James Wilsdon et al. 2015). Again, this discourse is deeply related to narratives of the informetrics and scientometrics. We have found that there is a strong tendency, to relate scholarly uses of social media to research to existing indicators of scientific output, e.g. publications and citations. This is not only reflected in theoretical considerations about how to interpret social media use and altmetrics but also in dominant practices of counting. What we could observe is a strong increase of scrutinization activities, where the coverage and distribution of various social media data sources are empirically investigated, mostly measured against existing indicators of influence such as citations. The greater a certain channel displays (positive) correlation

with citations and publications, the more likely it is that this channel is interpreted to indicate research performance. As a result, we do not only have a vast amount of correlation studies of Altmetrics data sources, but also a specific discursive context in which scholarly media use is presented and related to, that is, research impact and research impact measurement. This discourse shapes not only how Altmetrics is perceived, but also attributes value to the various channels of dissemination upon which the alternative indicators rest. We will come back later to that point.

A second discourse we have identified throughout the analysis of scholarly literature is the discourse on societal impact (Bornmann 2014, 2016; Cress 2014). The discourse on societal impact can be perceived as an alternative narrative or as counter-narrative of the research performance discourse. Contrary to the research performance, this discourse is particularly fuelled by policy discourse that tends to reflect growing expectations towards the uses and applications of science and technology. Similarly to the structure and pattern of the research performance discourse, we did not only find articles that generally articulate the societal value of novel channels of dissemination on a theoretical level, but also articles that used societal impact as an interpretive scheme. That is, whenever, a certain type of dissemination channel is not correlated to citations or publication coverage, these articles then tend to interpret this channel as indicating some 'other type of impact' or more often even 'societal impact'. While it is not often clear what societal impact means in these specific contexts, the data show that scholars need to relate to this discourse in some respect. Currently, we could not completely reconstruct, how this discourse emerged since it appears to go beyond the scholarly realm, nevertheless the dominance of its occurrence reveals its significance for scholarly dissemination strategies.

Thus, we have identified two discourses from scholarly literature that specify dimensions of how innovative dissemination is interpreted and positioned. We can assume that these discourses also influence perceptions of scholars.

3.2.2. Secondary analysis of survey results

The second source of information that feeds into the construction of dimensions related to dissemination channels results from a general survey that has been set up within OpenUP (see Appendix B). Almost 1000 scholars responded to the survey, coming from various disciplines, such as the natural sciences, engineering, but also medicine and the social sciences. Beside other items, the survey also asked for (traditional and innovative) channels of dissemination and altmetrics use as well as their disciplinary recognition (Question batteries Q3 and Q4). These findings allow for articulating which types of media are appreciated and how they are perceived in different disciplinary communities. We have grouped the different answers towards what channels of dissemination they appreciate to their disciplinary background and their sociodemographic characteristics. A detailed list of these activities will be provided in an upcoming report (Deliverable 5.4.)

The data reveal that there are strong field-specific differences towards the recognition, use, and appreciation of innovative dissemination channels. While the natural sciences and the engineering sciences often make less use of them, the social sciences and the humanities seem to be more informed and more likely to use these new formats (Q 3.5) though the use of these channels is still very low (with the exemption of academic social network sites). The data also reveal that appreciation of certain channels hinges to a large extent on which practices are appropriate in the respective field. For instance, we can see that traditional channels of dissemination are particularly favoured in the natural sciences where they are also most frequently used. In addition, there are also strong intergenerational differences, depending on the age of the scholars: The younger generations both in the social sciences and in the natural sciences, have a stronger tendency to use novel channels while they are also more aware of these channels (relating to 3.8). Thus, both of these dimensions, field specificity and

intergenerational assessment, structure how the channels are used and perceived. In an upcoming activity, we plan to map and to cluster these various qualities in order to further provide more specific information useful for characterizing a target audience for dissemination channels (see also Bailey 1994). For instance, it might be relevant to specifically focus on social sciences juniors or on natural sciences seniors in order to develop a dedicated dissemination strategy.

Finally, the survey results also revealed how dominant narratives and discourses literally influenced the perceptions of scholars, particularly in the perception of Altmetrics. This applies for the discourse on societal impact which is particularly dominant in the overall reading of innovative dissemination channels and altmetrics. Although only a few know what is meant by the term Altmetrics – only a third of the respondents know what it means exactly - a vast number of scholars interprets scholarly social media use to point at societal impact (responses related to Q 4.4. and 4.5.). This indicates a strong effect of the dominant discourse on the subject. It thereby validates our findings from the analysis of the scholarly literature and encourages us to this as a dimension for our dissemination channel taxonomy.

3.2.3. Qualitative interviews with experts in the field

As we do not know exactly how these interpretive patterns emerged and how the appreciation of value in these settings can be understood, we additionally draw on qualitative interviews with experts in scholarly social media use and altmetrics. These experts have been identified in a review about scholarly output which has been performed in Task 5.1. In addition, experts in the field of policy and research funding agencies have been integrated into the list to broaden the scope of interviewees (see Appendix C – the List of Interviewees). Until now, we have already developed a guideline for conducting semi-structured qualitative inquiry that is constantly improved (see Appendix for details). Currently, we are in the process of conducting interviews with these experts. The results of the interviews will be mapped and coded based on techniques of qualitative content analysis and presented in the final version of the taxonomy (Deliverable 5.4.). Though results of some of the interviews are preliminary, we can already present some of them which allow for deepening the dimensions identified in the review and the survey activity.

In an upcoming activity, the results of the interviews will be documented and transcribed. We will then iteratively summarize, analyze, and code the material applying methods of qualitative content analysis (Glaser, Strauss Anselm L. 2010; Kuckartz 2014). Beside the existing theoretical concepts, we have developed so far, we hope to derive some more subcodes in the material that specify the dimensions of appreciation and valuation of dissemination channels in this context. These information will also allow for constructing relations between the different dimensions developed so far (Bradley et al. 2007, p. 1766)

3.2.4. Analysis of metrics related to innovative channels of dissemination

Fourthly, we will also map metrics and metric activities that track and count different aspects of each dissemination channel and each service. In part, we can draw on previous knowledge gained within OpenUP (Deliverable 4.1. and 5.1.). This is done because, as we have argued in chapter 2, classifications from evaluative activities further contribute to value creation as they allow for comparison and putting certain qualities into an order or a range. By so doing, certain measurable aspects become more visible. In the field of innovative dissemination channels and altmetrics, these measuring activities are moderated and mediated by certain data providers who define what data sources from which channel are tracked and how this translates into a specific indicator. Thereby, certain aspects of social media use, specific assumptions about what constitutes value for scholarly communication are inscribed into every indicator. By linking these indicators to publisher sites and personal webpages, indicators such as the altmetric.com composite indicator, create visibility for a set or for a specific channel of

dissemination. In an upcoming activity, we plan to relate these data from metrics of the providers to information about scholarly perceptions of dissemination channels gained from the survey. We will thus be able, for instance, to provide information of whether a certain provider meets the expectations and appreciations of a specific field.

3.2.5. Documentation and analysis of stakeholder workshop

Finally, we have encouraged the communities to engage with the resulting taxonomy in a workshop held in Berlin. The goal of this task is to validate the taxonomy linking channels of dissemination and altmetrics indicators. Scholars from various disciplines, policy makers, research managers and altmetrics experts have been invited to discuss the findings. The workshop has been already held on the premises of the WPL and gained considerable awareness in the community. A detailed documentation of the report will be presented in a further report.

4. Presentation and integration of empirical inquiries in taxonomy of dissemination channels

The information generated in these different inquiries will then be finally used to define the taxonomy of dissemination channels. The different dimensions that have been mentioned so far will be further developed. The relations that come up between these dimensions will be further elaborated. The idea is for each specific function of novel dissemination channels (e.g. entertainment, organizing attribution, stabilizing knowledge and so on), a specification of a list of dimensions is provided that informs about certain aspects of its appreciation and valuation. By so doing, we aim to provide orientation for scholars who plan to develop a dissemination strategy and are unsure about how what might be relevant in this respect and how a certain choice of communication is appreciated within their community.

The information will be summarized in a table that will contain the following format and content (see table 1).

Table 1: Dissemination channel

Dimension	Service 1 e.g. Mendeley	Service 2	Service 3	Service 4
Discourse: Research performance		Highly related		Rarely related
Discourse: Societal impact	Highly related		Rarely related	
General Appreciation				
Metrics	Downloads Views	Followers	Views	Downloads
Provider coverage	X1, X2, X3	X1	X1, X2	X3
Intergenerational assessment				
Field specificity				

In a next step, we will provide an overview of data providers that relates the information gathered to dimensions of appreciation and context specific assessment. Thereby, we aim at providing an overview of how innovative channels of dissemination and altmetrics indicators are linked.

Table 2: Metric Provider (e.g. Altmetric.com)

OpenUP	Field specificity	Discourse	Participant3	Participant4
Metric 1: data source, metric				
Metric 2: data source, metric				
Metric 3: data source, metric				
Metric 4: data source, metric				

Source: provide the source of data (Cambria 10)

5. Conclusion and outlook

Our goal in this report was to provide a methodology to construct and present a taxonomy that links innovative channels of dissemination with alternative or open metrics. We have done so by providing a framework of how such a taxonomy can be constructed based on the theoretical approach of the sociology of valuation. Adopting this approach to the study of scholarly dissemination channels we came up with, acts of valuation specifying the phenomenon under study, that is, the appreciation of channels of dissemination, and discourses, routines, and classifications (metrics) as the building blocks which constitute the dimensions of the taxonomy. Subsequently, we provided a methodology of how we empirically aim to inform and further develop these dimensions. Within OpenUp, we can draw on various sources and activities that can enrich and deepen our taxonomy, e.g., analysis of scholarly literature, survey results, expert interviews, and the mapping of metrics. Finally, we aim at validating our taxonomy by debating it with relevant stakeholders. This will also include gender related aspects of online science communication.

We are currently at the stage of conducting interviews with experts and secondary analysis of survey data. In this process, some of the specification of the dimensions presented here may change. Nevertheless, we expect the overall structure of the taxonomy report (Deliverable 5.4.) to have similarities to proposed presentation of results.

Finally, our goal with this taxonomy is to inform and orient strategies of scholarly dissemination strategies. We hope that the derived taxonomy might also stimulate debate about the uses and problems with innovative channels of dissemination and their current counting practices. We are also aware that, by providing this information, our taxonomy will lend visibility and credibility to some of the channels and services presented here. We hope the taxonomy and the specifications finally provided therein can be used as a resource for reflection of these recent developments.

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Appendix A: Corpus of scholarly literature on innovation dissemination channels and altmetrics

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Appendix B Survey Questionnaire

1. Introduction

1.1. What is the core scientific discipline of your research?

Natural Sciences	
Engineering and Technology	
Medical Sciences	
Agricultural Sciences	
Social Sciences	
Humanities	
Other (please specify):	

1.2. Which stage of your career are you at?

First Stage Researcher (doctoral candidate stage or equivalent, without having undertaken a doctorate)	
Recognized Researcher (PhD holder or equivalent who is not yet fully independent; non-tenured assistant professor; post-doctoral stage)	
Established Researcher (researcher who has developed a level of independence; tenured assistant or associate professor; research specialist or manager, senior lecturer, senior scientist)	
Leading Researcher (researcher leading his/her research area or field; professor stage)	

1.3. What is your gender?

Male	
Female	
Prefer not to say	
Other	

1.4. What type of organisation do you currently work for? If you work for more than one organisation, please choose the one you consider to be your main employer.

University	
Research centre/institute	
Company	
Other type of organisation (please specify)	
Do not know/cannot answer	

1.4.a. What is the sector of this organisation?

Public or government sector	
Private, not-for-profit sector	
Private for-profit	
Other (please specify)	
Do not know/cannot answer	

1.5. How important to you are the research outputs listed below?

By important we mean the outputs which you produce most frequently, or outputs upon which your success as a researcher mostly relies on.

	Very important	Somewhat important	Neither important nor not important	Somewhat unimportant	Not important at all	Do not know / cannot answer
Peer-reviewed publications						
Books, book chapters, monographs						
Data, datasets (i.e. as primary output/goal of your research activities)						
Software, IT tools and applications						
Intellectual property rights (patents, trademarks, utility designs, etc.)						
Protocols, ontologies, guidelines, methodologies for practitioners						
Policy outputs (e.g. policy conclusions and recommendations, reports, briefs, etc.)						
Other research outputs (please specify)						

2. Peer review process

Peer review is a process in which qualified scientific experts (peers) scrutinise the research results and assess if they are valid, significant and original, and whether they can be published in a scholarly journal. Traditional/established peer review includes two review formats, including single-blind and double-blind review. The reviewer's identity is concealed in both cases, however the author's identity can either be known to the reviewer (single-blind review), or be concealed as well (double-blind review).

Open peer review (OPR) introduces a variety of innovations to the traditional peer review process. Primary aspects of OPR are: (1) Open Identities: authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity; (2) Open Reports: review reports are published alongside the relevant article; and (3) Open Participation: the wider community to able to contribute to the review process.

2.1. Do you have prior experience as the main author of at least one peer-reviewed publication?

Yes	
No	Filter to 2.2

2.1.a [if have experience as an author in 2.1]: Considering your overall experience as an author, how satisfied are you with the established peer review process?

Very satisfied	
Somewhat satisfied	
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	
Somewhat dissatisfied	

Very dissatisfied	
Do not know / cannot answer	

2.1.b. [if answered neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, somewhat dissatisfied or very dissatisfied in 2.1.a]: You have indicated a low or neutral overall satisfaction with the established peer review process in the previous question. How important are the reasons listed below behind your reservations with the established peer review system?

	Very important	Somewhat important	Neither important nor not important	Somewhat unimportant	Not important at all	Do not know / cannot answer
Quality of peer review reports						
Time/duration peer review takes						
Transparency issues, i.e. lack of openness in the process						
Lack of scientific communication between authors and reviewers						
Other reasons (please specify)						

2.1.c [if have experience as an author in 2.1] Which of the following peer review approaches would you choose to undergo for your own research outputs?

The approaches described on the left refer to open peer review approaches, while the ones on the right are practices which tend to occur under the currently established system. Please answer this question assuming that your own research outputs would have to undergo the peer review approaches described below.

	Strongly support open peer review	Rather in support of open peer review	Indifferent between the approaches	Rather in support of the established peer review	Strongly support the established peer review	
Open report: review report is published alongside the relevant article						Closed report: no review report is published alongside the relevant article
Open identity: authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity						Closed identity: neither the author's nor the reviewer's identity are disclosed
Open participation: a wider community of researchers contributes to peer review						Closed participation: only appointed peer reviewers contribute to peer review

Open platform: peer review is managed by a different organisation than the publishing body						Peer review is managed by the publishing body
Open pre-review: manuscripts are made available to researchers/public before formal peer review						No open pre-review: manuscripts are not made available to researchers/public before formal peer review
Open final-version commenting: review/commenting after publication						No final-version commenting after publication
Data review: datasets used/produced are accessible and reviewed along with the paper						No data review: accessible datasets typically are not reviewed along with the paper

2.1.d [if have experience as an author in 2.1] How frequently do you make your key research outputs openly accessible and free of charge to use?

	Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)	Most of the time (60-89% of the time)	Sometimes (40-59% of the time)	Rarely (11-39% of the time)	Never, or almost never (0-10% of the time)	Do not know / cannot answer
Scientific publications						
Books, book chapters, monographs						
Data, datasets (i.e. as primary output/goal of your research activities)						
Software, IT tools and applications						
Protocols, ontologies, guidelines, methodologies for practitioners						
Policy outputs (e.g. policy conclusions and recommendations)						
Other types of outputs (please specify)						

2.1.e. [if have experience as an author in 2.1] To what extent do these factors/barriers prevent you from making more of your research results openly accessible and free of charge to use?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To little or no extent at all	Do not know / cannot answer
Negative personal perceptions about open access					
My organisation encourages me to publish in traditional outlets/journals which have restricted access					
By publishing in open access outlets/journals I would likely negatively affect my career development and performance assessment in my organisation					
Lack of financial support to openly share my research results					
Lack of knowledge about open access platforms and services where my research results could be published					
Privacy and/or ethical concerns					
Other factors/barriers (please specify)					

2.2 Do you have prior experience as a reviewer of at least one peer-reviewed publication?

Yes	
No	Filter to 3.1

2.2.a. [if have experience as a reviewer in 2.2] To what extent do you agree with these statements considering your experience as a reviewer under the established peer review system?

	Strongly agree	Rather agree	Neither agree nor disagree	Rather disagree	Strongly disagree	Do not know / cannot answer
My work as a reviewer is being explicitly acknowledged and evaluated in my organisation						
My work as a reviewer benefits my career development						
My incentives to work as a reviewer would increase if my review comments were published under my name						

My incentives to work as a reviewer would increase if my review work was remunerated						
My incentives to work as a reviewer would increase if the peer review process became more collaborative with authors, editors and/or publishers						

3. Dissemination of research results

For the purposes of this survey, we define dissemination as follows:

Dissemination is a planned process that involves consideration of target audiences and the settings in which research findings will be shared. Where appropriate, dissemination involves communicating and interacting with wider audiences to facilitate research uptake in decision-making processes and practice.

3.1. How important is the dissemination of research results to non-research audiences (e.g. practitioners, citizens, journalists, policymakers, industry, etc.) in your specific research area?

Very important	
Rather important	
Neither important nor unimportant	
Rather unimportant	
Not important at all	
Do not know / cannot answer	

3.2. How often do you target the following audiences when disseminating your research findings?

	Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)	Most of the time (60-89% of the time)	Sometimes (40-59% of the time)	Rarely (11-39% of the time)	Never, or almost never (0-10% of the time)	Do not know / cannot answer
Researchers from my own discipline/area						
Researchers from other disciplines/areas						
Teachers						
Students						
Policy makers & government						
Practitioners						
Industry/business						
General public						
Journalists						
Charities/NGOs						
Children up to the age of 14						
Other (please specify)	free text box					

3.3. When do you usually start disseminating your research?

During the initial/inception phase of the research activities (i.e. shortly before or after the start of your research projects)	
During the main phase of the research activities (e.g. during data collection; field research, etc.);	
After conclusion of the research activities (i.e. end of project, publication of research results, etc.)	
Do not know/cannot answer	

3.4. How important are the following reasons when disseminating the findings of your research?

	Very important	Somewhat important	Neither important nor unimportant	Somewhat unimportant	Not important at all	Do not know / cannot answer
Contributing to the body of knowledge, enabling other researchers to build on top of my research						
Raising awareness of the findings						
Stimulating discussions and public understanding of science						
Receiving feedback on my research						
Influencing policymaking and practices by transferring my research results						
Justifying public funding of my research						
Attracting future funding						
Raising my own or my organisation's profile						
Dissemination is part of my performance assessments/evaluations in my organisation						
Improving my communication skills						
Satisfying contractual obligations (e.g. research funding)						
Other (Specify)						

3.5. Which of these channels listed do you use most frequently to disseminate your own research to reach your target groups?

	Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)	Most of the time (60-89% of the time)	Sometimes (40-59% of the time)	Rarely (11-39% of the time)	Never, or almost never (0-10% of the time)	Do not know/cannot answer

Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)						
Popular science publications (e.g. magazines)						
Academic conferences/workshops						
Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers						
Press releases						
Television/radio programs						
Open access repositories/ preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)						
Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)						
Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)						
Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube, Vimeo)						
Wikipedia						
Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)						
E-Mail/Newsletters						
Personal/Project Website						
Open lab books/interactive notebooks						
Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)						
Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)						
Exhibitions, performances						
Other (please specify)						

3.6. And how frequently do you use these sources to inform your professional work as a researcher?

	Always, or almost always (90-100% of the time)	Most of the time (60-89% of the time)	Sometimes (40-59% of the time)	Rarely (11-39% of the time)	Never, or almost never (0-10% of the time)	Do not know/cannot answer
Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)						
Popular science publications (e.g. magazines)						
Academic conferences/workshops						
Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers						
Press releases						
Television/radio programs						
Open access repositories/ preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)						
Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)						
Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)						

Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube)						
Wikipedia						
Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)						
E-Mail/Newsletters						
Personal/Project Website						
Open lab books/interactive notebooks						
Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)						
Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)						
Exhibitions, performances						
Other (please specify)						

3.7. Have you achieved any outstanding results by disseminating your research through dissemination channels other than traditional academic publishing, conferences and workshops in the past 5 years?

Yes
No

3.7.a [if answered yes]: Could you briefly describe your method and the success achieved? (open text)

Yes
In case of Yes: could you briefly describe your method and the success achieved?

3.7.b [if answered yes]: Would you agree if we contacted you via email for more details on your success story?

Yes
In case of Yes: could you briefly describe your method and the success achieved?
No

3.8. To what extent do you agree with the following statement: my research results successfully reach the key target groups

To a very large extent	
To a large extent	
To some extent	
To little or no extent at all	
Do not know / cannot answer	

3.8.a. To what extent do these factors prevent you from disseminating your results more effectively through non-traditional dissemination channels?

By non-traditional dissemination channels we mean channels other than traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books, monographs), conferences and workshops

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To little or no extent at all	Do not know / cannot answer
I do not need non-traditional dissemination to reach my target audiences.					
Time constraints					
Lack of financial support for non-traditional dissemination					
Lack of acknowledgement/credit given to non-traditional dissemination in my research field					
Lack of organizational support for non-traditional dissemination					
Lack of knowledge about non-traditional dissemination tools and methods					

Lack of presentation and communication skills					
Missing IT infrastructure					
Privacy and/or ethical concerns					
Legal/contractual barriers					
Other factors (please specify)					

4. Altmetrics & perceptions about dissemination channels

In the recent years “alternative metrics” or altmetrics have become a topic in the debate about a balanced assessment of research efforts as a complementary way of assessment beyond publication output and measures of reception via citation counts of peer-reviewed articles.

In the following section we want to assess, if such alternative metrics have become an important issue in your own work and your research field as a whole. In addition, we ask questions about the perceptions and potential of the different dissemination channels in your specific research area.

4.1. Are you aware of the term “alternative metrics” (altmetrics)?

Yes	
No	Filter to IV.4

4.1.a. Have you ever used alternative metrics in your work (e.g. to learn more about your own research profile or achievements, follow other researchers, find interesting research, etc.)?

Yes	
No	Filter to IV.3

4.2. To what extent do these statements apply to you?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To little or no extent at all	Do not know / cannot answer
I actively follow the development of alternative metric scores of my research					
I take measures to increase my alternative metrics scores					
I use alternative metrics to compare myself to other researchers					
I take alternative metrics into account when identifying interesting research					
I think that alternative metrics have an effect on how I am perceived as a researcher by others in my field of research					
Performance evaluations including alternative metrics would assess the achievements of my research in a more balanced way.					

4.3. To what extent do these factors prevent you from using alternative metrics in your work more actively?

	To a very large extent	To a large extent	To some extent	To little or no extent at all	Do not know / cannot answer

Lack of overall awareness of alternative metrics and their meaning/value in my organisation					
Lack of training on how to optimise my altmetrics scores					
Lack of awareness of tools and approaches which can show my altmetrics scores					
Lack of understanding of how alternative metrics scores are calculated and can be interpreted					
Other factors (please specify)					

4.4. Please rate how being represented in these dissemination activities is generally appreciated within your field of research (i.e. by your academic peers or organisation which employs you)

	Very appreciated	Moderately appreciated	Neither appreciated nor underappreciated	Moderately underappreciated	Not appreciated at all	Do not know/cannot answer
Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)						
Popular science publications						
Academic conferences/workshops						
Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers						
Press releases						
Television/radio programs						
Open access repositories/ preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)						
Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)						
Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)						
Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube, Vimeo)						
Wikipedia						
Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)						
E-Mail/Newsletters						
Personal/Project Website						

Open lab books/interactive notebooks						
Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)						
Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)						
Exhibitions, performances						
Other (please specify)						

4.5. Finally, what potential do the following dissemination channels have to lead to a wider societal impact?

	Very high potential	High potential	Some potential	Little or no potential	Do not know / cannot answer
Traditional academic publishing (e.g. academic journals, books)					
Popular science publications					
Academic conferences/workshops					
Events for the general public/specific target audiences other than researchers					
Press releases					
Television/radio programs					
Open access repositories/preprint servers (e.g. Zenodo, arXiv)					
Academic social networks (e.g. ResearchGate, Academia.edu)					
Non-specialist social networks (e.g. Facebook, Twitter)					
Podcasts, Video sharing sites (e.g. YouTube)					
Wikipedia					
Blogs, other wikis (excluding Wikipedia)					
E-Mail/Newsletters					
Personal/Project Website					
Open lab books/interactive notebooks					
Print media (e.g. leaflets, folders)					
Git repositories (e.g. GitHub)					
Exhibitions, performances					
Other (please specify)					

THANK YOU FOR YOUR ANSWERS!

Appendix C List of Expert Interviewees

ID	IID	Author Fullname	Organization	Country
73	1	Thelwall, Mike	Wolverhampton Univ	ENGLAND
22	2	Bornmann, Lutz	Max Planck Gesell	GERMANY
42 2	3	Lariviere, Vincent	Univ Montreal	CANADA
17 0	4	Peters, Isabella	ZBW Leibniz Informat Ctr Econ	GERMANY
41 9	5	Holmberg, Kim	Univ Turku	FINLAND
17 4	6	Gorraiz, Juan	Univ Vienna	AUSTRIA
49 0	7	Costas, Rodrigo	Leiden Univ	NETHERLAND S
42 1	8	Sugimoto, Cassidy	Indiana Univ	USA
57 4	9	Torres-Salinas, Daniel	Univ Navarra	SPAIN
33 4	10	Moed, Henk F.	Elsevier	NETHERLAND S
49 2	11	Wouters, Paul	Leiden Univ	NETHERLAND S
59 7	12	Bar-Ilan, Judit	Bar Ilan Univ	ISRAEL
80	13	Glanzel, Wolfgang	Katholieke Univ Leuven	BELGIUM

172	14	Lex, Elisabeth	Graz Univ Technol	AUSTRIA
754	15	Priem, Jason	Altmetric.com	USA
165	16	Ingwersen, Peter	Univ Copenhagen	DENMARK
	17	Büttgen, Stephan	Plum Analytics	
	18	???	ResearchGate	GERMANY
	19	???	Thomson Reuters	UK
	20	Price, Richard	Academia.edu	UK
	21	Wilsdon, James	University of Sheffield (also Altmetric.com)	UK
	22	Piwowar, Heather	Impactstory	USA
	23	Vaughan, Liwen	University of Ontario	USA
	24	Neylon, Cameron	Curtin University	AUSTRALIA
	25	Cronin, Blaise	Indiana University	USA
	26	Attenborough	PloS One	UK
ID	Records	Author Fullname	Organization	Country
81	27	Haustein, Stefanie	Univ Montreal	CANADA
178	28	Kousha, Kayvan	Wolverhampton Univ	ENGLAND
72	29	Haunschild, Robin	Max Planck Inst Solid State Res	GERMANY

418	30	Bowman, Timothy D.	Univ Montreal	CANADA
173	31	Gumpenberger, Christian	Univ Vienna	AUSTRIA
481	32	Fairclough, Ruth	Wolverhampton Univ	ENGLAND
211	33	Eysenbach, Gunther	TrendMD Inc	CANADA
88	34	Tattersall, Andy	SCHARR	ENGLAND
	34	Groth, Paul	Elsevier	NETHERLANDS
	35	Garfinkel, Michele	EMBO Journal, OSPP	GERMANY, USA
	36	Berghans, Stephan	ELSEVIER	NETHERLANDS
	37	Tochtermann, Klaus	ZBW, OSPP	GERMANY
	38	Matteo Razzanelli	Policy Adviser at European Research Council	BELGIUM
	39	Marco Malgarini	Senior Manager for Research Evaluation	BELGIUM
	40	Thomas Jørgensen	European University Association, Senior Policy Coordinator,	BELGIUM
	41	Harriman, Stephanie	Editor at BioMed Central	UK
	42	Dawson, Stephanie	CEO Science Open Platform	Germany
	43	Wille, Eva	Wiley VCH	USA

Appendix C: Interview Guideline: Innovative Channels of Dissemination and Altmetrics

- 1) As a short intro: Do you use innovative channels of dissemination (social media tools, open science tools, non-scholarly resources) to communicate your research?
- 2) Do you use Altmetrics on your own (for comparing your research with others or to increase visibility), for any other specific purpose)?
- 3) According to your perception, how are these channels used in your specific field of research? How are metrics that build upon these channels used?
- 4) Do you think there are specific choices/challenges of Altmetrics usage?

General Assessment and Perception of Dissemination Channels and Altmetrics

- 5) In more general terms, how do you perceive the Altmetrics movement (is it a hype, a new discipline, or community, or simply a new topic for scholars), what is it in your terms?
- 6) What are the main drivers/actors in diffusing Altmetrics in research and practice?
- 7) When reflecting about these descriptions, do you think you have a specific perspective towards Altmetrics? Could you describe that in more detail?

Data sources

- 8) There are now various providers for social media use and Altmetrics: Which of them do you consider most relevant (according to your field, your experience, from a more general stance)?
- 9) Altmetrics providers use many different data sources: Which are most relevant and why?
- 10) How do these different channels of dissemination become relevant and more visible?
- 11) As a scholar, on what basis should I decide how to use these data sources?
- 12) How do you perceive the way data sources in Altmetrics are aggregated and collected - are there any systematic problems or choices?
- 13) How do you perceive the role of these platform providers in Altmetrics? Will they have an impact on how data are collected?

Evaluation and Impact Assessment

- 14) Currently, there is a dominant debate that relates the use of innovative channels of dissemination to research performance and impact measurement. From your perspective as an expert in the field, is there an influence of Altmetrics on measuring research impact or research performance? How would you describe such influence?
- 15) Does this debate change the way innovative channels of dissemination are perceived?
- 16) What else can be said about the relationships to scientometrics, bibliometrics, and librarianship if any?
- 17) Can Altmetrics research contribute to scientometrics and evaluative bibliometrics?
- 18) Currently, some scholars use the phrase of “societal impact” to circumscribe the impact Altmetrics can have on other, non-scholarly audiences? What is your perception towards this topic?

Public Understanding of Altmetrics

- 19) How would you describe the public understanding and societal debate of Altmetrics
- 20) There is also the perception of Altmetrics propagators that it can help to make science more open and transparent? What do you think about these claims and expectations?
- 21) **Problems, Challenges related to Altmetrics?**